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Research Article

**A MULTICENTRE ASSESSMENT OF SUSTAINED RELEASE
OXPRENOLOL IN THE TREATMENT OF HYPERTENSION
IN OTD-PATIENT PRACTICE****Dr Muhammad Umar Rasool, Dr Zarmina Fatima, Dr Muhammad Faisal Ejaz**
Lahore General Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: Fifty-six patients with moderate essential hypertension (with diastolic blood pressure values between 106-120 mm Hg) showed inadequate control, problematic side effects, or a combination of both. Were selected for the study. Recently diagnosed patients and patients who discontinued treatment were also included in the study.

Place and Duration: In the Lahore General Hospital Lahore for six months duration from July 2019 to December 2019.

Methods: This study included 56 patients. The regimen consisted of 160mg of Oxprenolol in sustained release formulation (Trasicor 160 SR.) and 25mg of Chlorthalidone (Hygroton) administered once daily in the morning, for eight weeks. The mean duration of hypertension was five years, and the mean heart rate and blood pressure at the beginning of the study were 93- and 177/112-mm Hg, respectively.

At the end of the study, mean heart rate and blood pressure were 77- and 145/89-mm Hg, respectively. 45 of 45 patients (80%) had diastolic hypotension of 95 mm Hg or less. Adverse reactions were observed in 10 patients (17.9%) and were mild; in no case was it necessary to discontinue treatment earlier due to adverse reactions.

Conclusion: This study showed a combination of Oxprenolol slow release (Trasicor 160 SR.) and 25 mg chlorthalidone (Hygroton) administered once daily cause normalization of blood pressure in about 80% of patients and a single morning dose of sustained release formulation in a patient in moderate essential hypertension improves compliance.

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INTRODUCTION:

Beta receptor contenders are usually used to treat primary hypertension. On the way to achieve a pleasing healing response, they are usually prescribed two or else three times a day and can be combined with vasodilators, adrenergic, diuretics neuron methyl dopa and blockers¹. Various reports (Blackwell, "1973; Galley, 2009; Ayd, 2011) show that as the frequency of dosing increases, compatibility with treatment decreases².

Oxsprenolol is a beta blocker with effective antihypertensive properties³. The duration of action is longer than the plasma concentration suggests, but probably does not exceed 8-12 hours (Brunner et al⁴. 2010). Oxsprenolol is usually used two to three times a day to achieve a therapeutic antihypertensive effect⁵. The disadvantage of daily multiple doses is worrying when long-term treatment is needed, as is primary hypertension. West et al⁶. (1976) showed that 160 mg sustained release oxprenolol was produced similarly to 80 mg traditional oxprenolol and produced maximum blood levels at almost the same rate⁷. High compound concentrations also last much longer and are associated with a prolonged beta-blocking effect that lasts up to 24 hours⁸. Therefore, the goal of extending the half-life of the drug was achieved by developing a sustained release formulation⁹. An additional advantage is the reduction in maximum concentration, thus minimizing a significant decrease in heart rate and possible fatigue that may occur when plasma levels are high during exercise (Owens, 2012)¹⁰.

Chlorthalidone is a commonly used diuretic to treat high blood pressure. Because it has a long duration of action, once-daily dosing seems appropriate¹¹.

Beta-blockers reduce cardiac output and diuretics at least reduce peripheral resistance during long-term administration (Lund-Johansen, 2016; Simpson, 2014). In addition, beta-blockers may attenuate the renin-stimulating effect of diuretics and attenuate the hypokalemic effect (Hettiarachchi et al¹², 2015). Most authorities agree that beta blockers and

diuretics are groups of drugs with different modes of action that are useful in treating moderate hypertension. Although a wide range of dose levels can be used, in practice 160 mg of oxprenolol in combination with 25 mg of chlorthalidone appears to be an effective dose (Raftery, Elsdon Dew et al¹⁴). Hence this study was designed to examine the feasibility of substituting once-daily treatment with sustained release oxprenolol hydrochloride and chlorthalidone in group of hypertensive patients whose current treatment was giving inadequate blood pressure control, troublesome side-effects or a combination of both. This study is an open assessment of the general conditions of practice for individual physicians, each of whom may have a maximum of five patients.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was held in Lahore General Hospital Lahore for six months' duration from July 2019 to December 2019. The study included patients with moderate essential hypertension (with diastolic back pressure values between 106-120 mm Hg), inadequate monitoring of current treatment, problematic side effects, or a combination of both. Recent cases and patients who discontinued treatment were also included. The regimen contained 160 mg oxprenolol (TRASICOR 160 SR) in a sustained release formulation and 25 mg chlorthalidone (HY-GROTON) administered once a day in the morning for eight weeks. All patients were regularly monitored at two-week intervals. The blood pressure and pulse rate were recorded and tolerance was assessed, the nature, duration and severity of any adverse effects were recorded.

RESULTS:

The final analysis reported 56 cases, average age 52 years (26-75 years), 30 men and 26 women. The mean duration of hypertension was five years and the mean arterial pressure at the beginning of the study was 177/112 mm Hg. Heart rate and blood pressure results are shown in Table I.

Table 1: Heart Rate and Blood Pressure During Trial

Parameter		Pretrial	Week 2	Week 4	Week 6	Week 8
		Heart Rate	Mean	93	82	79
b/min	St. Dev.	14.3	10.9	10.2	10.2	8.5
Systolic B.P.	Mean	177	162	155	148	145
(mm of Hg)	St. Dev.	25.1	23.6	18.0	16.0	16.7
Diastolic B.P.	Mean	112	100	95	92	89
(mm of Hg)	St. Dev.	11.9	10.8	9.7	8.6	8.2

The mean heart rate at the beginning of the study was 93 and 77 at the end. The mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure at the beginning of the study were 177- and 112-mm Hg, respectively, and 145- and 89-mm Hg at the end of the study. At the end of the study, 45 of 56 patients (80%) had diastolic suppression of 95 mm Hg or less.

Table 2: Duration of Hypertension

Duration of Hypertension	No. of Cases
Less than 1 Year	18
1-5 Years	20
6-10 Years	5
Above 10 Years	6
Unknown	7

Table II shows the duration of hypertension in 56 patients; The average duration of hypertension is five years.

Table 3: Preference of Therapy

Preference	No. of Patients	%age
Trasicor SR	43	77%
No Preference	12	21%
Original Therapy	1	2%

Table III shows treatment preferences. At the end of the study, each patient was asked for a treatment preference. Forty-three patients (77%) preferred TRASICOR 160 SR, 12 patients did not, and one patient preferred primary treatment.

Table 4: Absolute Reduction Expressed as Percentage

Parameter	Pre/Trial	Completion of Trail	Absolute Reduction Expressed In %
Pulse	93	77	17%
Diastolic B.P. (mm of Hg)	112	89	21%
Systolic B.P. (mm of Hg)	177	145	18%

Table IV shows the absolute reduction in pulse rate and systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Pulse frequency decreased by 16.4%, systolic blood pressure by 182% and diastolic blood pressure by 20.55%.

Table 5: Previous Therapy

1	Beta Blocker (conventional)	3
2	Methyldopa (monotherapy)	17
3	Vasodilators (monotherapy)	Nil
4	Diuretics (monotherapy)	5
5	Combination Therapy	16
6	Therapy Not Known	8
7	No Therapy	7

Table V shows details of previous therapy. 17 patients were on methyldopa monotherapy and 16 on combination therapy.

Table 6: Unwanted Effects

Symptoms	Severity	No. of Patients
Weakness	Mild	5
Dryness of Mouth	Mild	1
Headache & Nausea	Moderate	1
Drowsiness	Moderate	2
Numbness of Extremities	Mild	1

Table VI shows the adverse reactions observed in ten patients (17.9%); weakness was the "most common side effect" and was seen in 5 patients.

DISCUSSION:

It is well known that the prognosis of hypertension can be improved by appropriate treatment, provided that patients take regularly prescribed medications (Dollery and Bulpitt, 2015). Patient cooperation in intact antihypertensive treatment is one of the most important factors in achieving satisfactory blood pressure control⁸. The percentage of patients who stop taking antihypertensive drugs has been shown to increase to 50% in the first year of treatment and to around 70% in 4 years (Cladwell et al¹⁵, 2012; Haynes and Sackctt, 2016). The need to take the daily number of pills for a long time often causes poor sleep (Havnes and Sackctt, 2016).

CONCLUSION:

Our results confirm that the daily combination of Oxprenolol + chlorthalidone is well tolerated and allows normalization of diastolic blood pressure (less than 95 mm Hg) in 70% of hypertensive patients (Zan-chetti et al., 2014). This study showed that the combination of slow release oxrenolol and chlortalidone administered once daily resulted in normalization of blood pressure in approximately 80% of patients with moderate hypertension.

REFERENCES:

- Jaffer, N. A. "A Multicentre Evaluation of Sustained Release Oxprenolol in the Management of Hypertension in Otd-Patient Practice."
- Gardezi, S. A. R., Abdul Majeed Chaudhary, Ghulam Akbar Sial, Ijaz Ahmad, Naweed Bhatti, Suhail Arif, and Shehlah Haroon. "Metronidazole in Anaerobic Surgical Infections."
- Cladwell, J.R., Coob, S. Dowling. (1970) The dropout problem in anti-hypertensive treatment. *J. Chron. Dis.*, 22:579
- Forrest, W. A. "A multicentre evaluation of sustained release oxprenolol in the management of hypertension in hospital out-patient practice." *Journal of International Medical Research* 6, no. 2 (1978): 136-140.
- Elsdon-Dew, R.W., Murphy, J.E., Ebbut, A.F. (1978) Trasidrex (A fixed combination of slow Trasacor 160mg and Navidrex 0.25mg) in treatment of hypertension. A multicentre Clinical Trial in General Practice. *Journal Int. Med. Res.*, 6:494.
- Haynes, R.B., Sackett, D.L. Compliance with therapeutic regimens. Baltimore John Hopkins University Press, 1976.
- Lund-Johansen, P. (1970), Hemodynamic changes in long-term diuretic therapy in essential hypertension; a comparative study of Chlorthalidone, polythiazide and hydrochlorothiazide. *Acta Med. Scand.*, 187:509
- Raftery, E.B. (1978) A controlled trial of Oxprenolol and diuretics in management of hypertension. *Modern Medicine-Supplement*, April 1978, 32.
- Owens, C.W.I. (1978) Sustained release beta-blockade. *Clin. Ther.*, 1:319.
- Simpson, F.O. (1974) Beta-adrenergic receptor blocking drugs in hypertension. *Drugs*, 7:85
- West, M.J., Kendall, M.J., Mitchard, M. and Faragher, B.B. (1976) A comparison of slow-release with conventional oxprenolol: plasma concentrations and clinical effects. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* 3:439.
- Zanchetti, A., Basagni, M., Buoninconti, R., Cherchi, A., Pessivva, A.C., Portioli, I., Prati, P., Rubegni, M., Selvini, A. and Motolese, M. (1976) Fixed combination of oxprenolol and chlorthalidone in hypertension: results of a comparative trial, in abstracts of the VIIth European Congress of Cardiology, Amsterdam II P. 71.
- Ayd, F.J, Jr. (1974) Single daily dose of antidepressant. *JAMA.*, 230:363
- Blackwell, B. (1973) Patient compliance. *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 289:249.
- Brunner, L., Imhof, P. and Jack, D. (1975) Relation between plasma concentrations and cardiovascular effects of oral oxprenolol in man. *Europ. J. Clin. Pharmacol.*, 8:3.